

Metal-Coated 3D-Printed Waveguide Devices for mm-Wave Applications

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Modern 3D printing technologies, also known as *additive manufacturing*, have evolved rapidly in recent years and are currently used in a wide range of engineering applications. In particular, the use of the new manufacturing techniques is leading to the development of very promising 3D electromagnetic structures for millimeter-wave (mm-wave) devices [1]. Thanks to the very competitive performance of 3D

printing in electromagnetic structures, both the industrial and research communities are paying special attention to this manufacturing technique, a novel fabrication process for polymer, metal, and ceramic materials. The technique is an attractive option for innovative and complex part fabrication, providing improvements in customization, part compactness, and rapid prototyping as well as reduced weight, cost, and mass production lead time.

In the literature, we find a variety of recent publications on waveguides [2]–[7], antennas [8]–[14], filter components [15], and other passive devices [16]–[20] over a wide range of frequencies using different 3D fabrication techniques. Most common 3D-printing techniques use plastics or ceramics, such as stereolithography apparatus (SLA) [2], [3], [5], [6], [8], [15], fused deposition modeling (FDM) [3], selective laser sintering (SLS) [13], [14], and Polyjet [16]–[19]. The FDM technique is the best known and most economical, but the resulting pieces have a finish that is not acceptable for use in mm-wave bands

due to the appearance of very marked grooves produced by the deposition of the plastic filament. The other techniques based on plastic or ceramics generally provide a good finish and a high level of detail in the printed structures. SLA is based on curing photoresins with ultraviolet (UV) light by means of a laser that sweeps the desired surface layer by layer. In the case of SLS, a laser is also used to heat and bond small plastic particles so that a rigid structure can be sintered. The Polyjet technique uses the traditional concept of inkjet printing in which the ink is replaced by a polymer that is cured with UV light when it comes into contact with the desired surface. These processes then need to be metal-coated for 3D electromagnetic structure parts.

Copper is commonly used for metal coating, due to its easier application process compared with other metals and its good electrical conductivity. Alternatively, direct 3D metal printing can be used, with processes such as binder jetting (BJ) [11], [12], [20], metal selective laser melting (SLM) [7], [12], and direct metal laser sintering (DMLS) [6], [9], [10] in stainless steel, aluminum, titanium, nickel, or copper. The BJ technique is similar to a Polyjet's; it dispenses an adhesive substance to bind metal particles and, therefore, does not require high-temperature conditions. For SLM and DMLS, high temperatures are required during the building of the parts to combine the metallic particles. The difference between these two technologies is the temperature applied. For DMLS, a laser beam scans the desired surface to bond each layer of the object. This process is performed in a chamber maintained at a temperature just below the melting temperature so that the passage of the laser raises the temperature enough to bond the metal particles. For SLM, the temperature must completely melt the particles to result in a robust and dense metal structure without porosity. Some studies have analyzed the structural differences between SLM and DMLS [21], [22]. Each technology, based on plastics, ceramics, and metals, has advantages and disadvantages with different impacts depending on the application.

All solutions based on metal printing provide great robustness but have a rough finish due to the size of the metal particles; this has a very negative impact on losses in high-frequency devices. However, it is possible to achieve a smoother surface finish by applying expensive postprocessing. Techniques in plastic or ceramics provide high resolution, except for FDM, the low resolution of which is not recommended for high-frequency applications. Polyjet generates surfaces with an appreciable roughness due to the accumulation of small resin droplets produced by the jetting process. In SLS, there is also a high level of roughness due to the size of the sintered plastic particles. SLA provides the best results in terms of both resolution and smoothness of surfaces; the shrinkage and bending problems that occur with SLA can be compensated for during the manufacturing process.

This article presents several aspects of the metal-coated SLA fabrication method with different polymers and ceramic materials and metal-coating techniques. It compares various metal-coated 3D-printed waveguide devices using groove gap waveguide technology and classical rectangular waveguides, such as WR-10 and WR-28. Simulation and prototype measurements of transmission and reflection coefficients are presented at the mm-wave bands from 30 to 110 GHz. Performances in terms of feasibility, materials selection, metal-coating thickness, roughness, losses, and weight are also discussed.

Gap Waveguide Technology

Gap waveguide technology was introduced in [23], and an overview of the technology, its current development, and future applications in mm-wave systems can be found at [24]. This technology is based on the use of periodic structures of metal pins that generate a high-impedance surface over them in a given frequency range. If a metal plate is placed on this surface at a distance of less than a quarter of a wavelength, all electromagnetic propagation is blocked, resulting in an electromagnetic band gap. This absence of metal-to-metal contact is a major advantage because waveguided structures can be created by replacing the metal side walls with these periodic pin structures. In this way, it is possible to avoid problems due to the bad electrical contacts that usually appear at mm-wave bands and facilitates both the design and assembly of power distribution networks.

A rectangular waveguide has an equivalent version in gap waveguide called a *groove gap waveguide (GGW)*, the structure of which is analyzed in [25]. Many designs of microwave and mm-wave devices and antennas based on gap waveguide can be found in the literature, such as [26]–[30]. However, gap waveguide also has some disadvantages. The need for several rows of periodic pins on each side of the waveguide significantly increases the size of this type of structure, which makes it very complicated to design arrays of radiant elements that are close enough to avoid grating lobes. Another disadvantage is the high cost of manufacturing this complex lattice of metal pins using classic computer numerical control (CNC) milling technologies in aluminum. Gap waveguide is therefore an ideal candidate for testing the potential of 3D printing and also for reducing the cost of prototyping. An extensive analysis of the properties of GGW-based prototypes manufactured with CNC and 3D-printing technologies can be found in [2].

The basic GGW structure for the designs discussed in this article, together with the values of the design parameters, is presented in Figure 1. The chosen structure has three rows of pins on the sides, providing a field attenuation in the last row greater than 50 dB. The behavior of the propagation constant β of the excited modes in both the GGW and the equivalent rectangular waveguide is depicted in Figure 2. The figure shows how the periodic pins block the propagation between approximately 20 and 40 GHz, and there is a single mode band between 23 and 40 GHz in which the TE_{10} mode propagates as well as in the rectangular waveguide model.

Groove Gap Waveguide Prototypes at Ka Band

This section presents the GGW structures designed and manufactured for this article. We manufactured a total of six pieces from different companies and with

different materials, resolutions, and metallization processes to determine which aspects to account for when comparing the measured results with the simulations. The design, represented in Figure 3, contains a part with a straight GGW section and a four-way power di-

Figure 1. The basic GGW structure used for the prototypes designed in this article: (a) a view of the design parameters $h = 0.6$ mm, $D = 1$ mm, $W = 8$ mm, $p = 2.6$ mm, and $d = 3$ mm and (b) a view of the paths where the propagation is allowed or forbidden.

Figure 2. A dispersion diagram of the GGW unit cell (solid lines) and the equivalent rectangular waveguide (dashed lines). The total height of both structures is 3.6 mm, while the width of the equivalent rectangular waveguide (eq. WR) for the same cutoff frequency of the TE_{10} mode is 6.51 mm.

vider. The most relevant dimensions are indicated, but if readers wish to consult all the parameters and simulated results individually for each part of the section and the divisor, these can be found in [2].

As the prototypes were manufactured by SLA and subsequent metallization, it is important to know the available materials and metallization processes used for plastic coating, as discussed in the following

Figure 3. A representation model of the manufactured prototypes. This model includes a straight GGW section and a four-way power divider.

Figure 4. Metal-coated prototypes. The identification (ID) numbers refer to those in Table 1. Each prototype has one straight waveguide section 90 mm in length and a four-way power divider with an input to output length of 106.5 mm.

section on selecting materials. A comparison of the most critical structural details of the prototypes is provided in the "Structural Details" section, and the measurements and simulation with different levels of effective roughness of the metal-coated surfaces are compared in the section "Measurements and Comparison Among Prototypes."

Selecting Materials and Metal Coating

The materials chosen were light-sensitive resins that harden in the presence of UV light because all the pieces for this article were manufactured using an SLA process. The base material selected for 3D-printed prototypes is important and depends on the application. There are elastic, impact resistant, waterproof, or high-temperature resistant materials available. For our purposes, they needed to be rigid and easily postprocessed to apply a thin metal layer on their surface. The materials available vary depending on the company we work with, but we chose those recommended by the manufacturing companies.

Regarding the metallization of plastic parts, it is recommended that the thickness of the metal be greater than seven times the skin depth of the metal at the working frequency. For reference, the skin depth of copper at Ka band is between 0.33 and 0.4 μm , so metallization should be at least 3 μm . Figure 4 compares six prototypes manufactured with different materials and metallization. All information on materials, layer resolution, and metal coating of the different prototypes, as well as the companies that manufactured them, are shown in Table 1.

Of all the materials selected, Nanotool (which has now been replaced by Perform with enhanced properties) has good thermal resistance properties and can withstand temperatures of more than 200 °C. This is of interest in possible component designs for satellites that must withstand high temperatures due to sunlight, which is the reason we included this material. Another important factor is the metal-coating process; we tried three different pro-

cesses: electroplating, electroless, and vacuum coating technology.

The electroplating technique, as its name indicates, uses electrical charges to deposit a metallic layer on the material. The surfaces are first treated so that the metal ions can be deposited on them. These are dissolved in a chemical solution and circulated from the anode to the cathode; therefore, the part to be metallized must be connected to the cathode. The electroless technique is simpler; instead of using electricity, the metal is deposited with an autocatalytic reaction

by immersing the part in a solution having a reducing agent. In [31], a comparison between the electroplating and electroless processes is provided. Vacuum coating technology consists of the evaporation of aluminum ions deposited on the surface of the piece inside a vacuum chamber. The thickness of the metallic layer obtained using this technique is under than $1\ \mu\text{m}$. More information about vacuum coating can be found in [32]. Only prototype 6 was metallized using

vacuum coating, as indicated in Table 1. Because the thickness of this type of coating is several nanometers, well below the value of seven times the skin depth, an anomalous performance is expected.

Structural Details

One of the key steps in any manufacturing technology is to reproduce the designed model as faithfully as possible. In this section, we present a structural analysis

TABLE 1. Materials and metal coatings.

ID	Material	Layer Resolution (μm)	Metal Coating	Company	Country
1	Nanotool	100	Electroplating copper (Cu), $50\ \mu\text{m}$	Protolabs USA Repliform Inc.	United States
2	Accura SL 5530	50	Electroplating Cu, $50\ \mu\text{m}$	Protolabs USA Repliform Inc.	United States
3	Accura SL 5530	100	Electroplating Cu, $50\ \mu\text{m}$	Protolabs USA Repliform Inc.	United States
4	Accura SL 5530	100	Electroplating Cu, $10\ \mu\text{m}$	Protolabs Europe	France/Germany
5	Material D	100	Electroless Cu, $3\text{--}5\ \mu\text{m}$	Swissto12	Switzerland
6	VisiJet SL Clear	100	Vacuum coating Al, $\ll 1\ \mu\text{m}$	Balentec SL WAAM SL	Spain

Figure 5. Microphotographs of the prototypes. (a)–(d) The top row shows a single pin, (e)–(h) the middle row shows the corner of the transition to WR-28, and (i)–(l) the bottom row shows the metal surface in higher detail. The first column [(a), (e), and (i)] is associated with the prototypes manufactured in the United States (1, 2, and 3 in Table 1), the second [(b), (f), and (j)] with those manufactured in France/Germany (ID 4 in Table 1), the third [(c), (g), and (k)] with those manufactured in Switzerland (ID 5 in Table 1), and the right-hand column with those manufactured in Spain (ID 6 in Table 1).

of the critical parts of the prototypes. Figure 5 shows microphotographs of the cylindrical pins and corners of the rectangular waveguide transitions together with the metal surface. Some samples show slight disturbances in the circularity of the pins, with a diameter of 1 mm. In general, the deviations are minimal, on the order of a few tens of microns.

It is interesting to note the level of precision with which the corners of the transitions have been obtained. This ability to reproduce corners at such right angles is far superior to that available with CNC. It should be noted that the metallization achieved is smooth and very homogeneous in all cases except with that of vacuum coating technology. Figure 5(d) and (h) shows how the metal accumulates most at the transition edges and at the circular edge of the pin, which is typical of this metallization method. In these areas, it is clear that the thickness of metallization is well above the manufacturer's stated value but rapidly decreases to thicknesses below $1\ \mu\text{m}$ on flat surfaces.

With regard to the metal surfaces presented in the bottom row of Figure 5, it is important to mention that the roughness achieved is critical to reduce losses in the conductor [33]. In this respect, it is necessary to differentiate between roughness and waviness [34], which is given on a larger spatial scale (see DIN EN ISO 4287 in [35]). An in-depth discussion of the concepts of roughness and waviness is addressed at the end of this section. The appearance of the samples in Figure 5 (i) and (j) is similar, with significant granularity but with a bright appearance, which is indicative of low roughness [36]. The aluminum sample in Figure 5(l) is lacking in metallization and shows dark, uncoated areas. Finally, the sample in Figure 5(k) has very low granularity (low waviness) but lacks brightness, which is directly related to a higher roughness.

A view of one transition of each prototype is shown in Figure 6, which presents the structural details of the six prototypes in Table 1. All have very smooth surfaces and shiny metallizations. In Figure 6(b) and (c), we can see some undulation in the surface that may be due to surface alignment imperfections during the 3D-printing process. The difference in finishes due to the metal-coating processes applied is notable.

These smooth and homogeneous surfaces have been achieved because the pieces have been printed horizontally. However, if the part to be printed has a larger area, it may be necessary to print the part at an angle to avoid severe shrinking and bending. This was necessary for the prototype analyzed in [2], as the dimensions of the part were considerably larger and the plastic layers would contract during the curing process. Figure 7 shows a detailed image of the surfaces when the piece is printed at an angle. Cylindrical supports were included in the prototypes

shown in Figure 6 to ensure that the plastic does not deform when the flanges are screwed together to measure the parts. The prototype in Figure 7 did not include these supports, which made the measurement process difficult.

The prototype in Figure 7 demonstrates the concepts of waviness and roughness mentioned previously. The surface profile of this part was measured, and the result is shown in Figure 8. From this measurement of the piece profile, both roughness and waviness can be extracted by applying a filter as recommended in [35]. There is a higher level called *form*, which in this case is a horizontal line and is not represented in the graphs. To obtain the form, a deeper

Figure 6. A detailed view of the transition to rectangular waveguide WR-28 in each of the six prototypes. (a)–(f) correspond, respectively, to IDs 1–6 in Table 1.

Figure 7. A detailed view of the resin layers in the prototype analyzed in [2].

Figure 8. (a) An extraction of the waviness and roughness of a measured profile. (b) The measured profile is shown as the sum of waviness and roughness. The profile corresponds to the prototype in Figure 7, where the measured roughness is multiplied by a factor of seven to be visible in the curves as an example.

Figure 9. The normalized distribution of the measured roughness in the Figure 8 example. The measurement fits very well with a normal distribution exhibiting a standard deviation of $2.1 \mu\text{m}$.

filtering is necessary to eliminate the imperfections coming from the waviness. To calculate the effect of roughness on electromagnetic losses in metallic structures, the value of roughness root mean square (RMS) is usually used. The result of the measured roughness distribution is fitted with the normal distribution. The standard deviation of this fitted distribution corresponds to the measured RMS roughness, as shown in Figure 9.

Finally, the bending of the plastic layers can be very negative. This effect is produced by the progressive curing of the plastic layers, and it is most likely to occur in flat and larger pieces. Some of the manufactured prototypes in this study experienced considerable bending, which coincides with those having irregularities on their surfaces. Therefore, these two types of manufacturing deviations may be related and so need further investigation.

In Figure 10, this bending effect is compared to other pieces that did not bend. Fortunately, this bending can be corrected by tightly screwing the part to a rigid aluminum plate. The result depends very much

Figure 10. A lateral view of (a) prototype 1 without bending and (b) prototype 2 bended.

on the characterization of the processes the company has carried out to compensate for this bending as well as on the material chosen. It is recommended at the design level that the relationship between the largest lateral side and the height of the piece to be printed does not exceed a value of 30. On the other hand, printing the piece at an angle helps minimize bending, in return for which a waviness on the surface produced by the stacked layers of plastic is introduced, as shown in Figure 7.

Measurements and Comparison Among Prototypes

This section shows the measurement results of the prototypes compared with simulations. Figure 11 de-

picts the results of the straight waveguide sections, and Figure 12 shows the results of the four-way dividers. Figures 11(a) and 12(a) show the reflection coefficient, Figures 11(b) and 12(b) the transmission coefficient, and Figures 11(c) and 12(c) a zoomed view of the transmission coefficient of the copper-coated pieces. Finally, Figure 11(d) depicts the simulation of the straight section considering different values of roughness of the copper plating to compare with the measured levels in Figure 11(c).

A large discrepancy can be seen in the measurement of the transmission coefficient from prototype 6 with respect to the others. This result is expected, as the thickness of the metal coating of this prototype is much lower than recommended to ensure a good metallic performance. The difference in loss of prototype 6 compared to prototypes 1–5 is 6–9 dB in the center of the band, as shown in Figures 11(b) and 12(b). Because the reflection coefficient in Figures 11(a) and 12(a) is low, we conclude that most of the power injected into the prototype is dissipated into the structure. We have ensured that the losses fit very well with the simulation when considering a metal coating with a very low conductivity of $\sigma = 4 \cdot 10^3$ S/m. The results obtained with prototypes

Figure 11. Simulations (SIM) and measurements (IDs 1–6) of the straight waveguide section for the six prototypes: (a) the reflection, (b) the transmission, (c) a detailed view of the measured transmission, and (d) a detailed view of the simulated transmission with roughness RMS values of 0–1.8 μm .

per unit length are in the range of 2–4.5 dB/m, without considering prototype 6.

Comparison of Rectangular Waveguide WR-28 and WR-10 Prototypes

This final section compares copper-coated 3D-printed and commercial sections of the WR-28 and WR-10 waveguides as a complement to the measurements made for the prototypes based on GGW in the “Groove Gap Waveguide Prototypes at Ka Band” section. We manufactured two waveguide sections for comparison with their commercial counterparts using copper-coated SLA in Swissto12. Sections WR-28 and WR-10, printed and commercial, are shown in Figure 13.

The measured results of the waveguides in Figure 13 are shown in Figure 14(a) and (b), which depicts the response of the WR-28 waveguides and of the WR-10 waveguides, respectively. The results obtained are summarized in Table 3, which shows the average losses per unit length in each of the waveguides and the weight in grams of each piece. The behavior of the 3D-printed sections is positive, although equivalent roughness differs between prototypes.

In the case of WR-28, the 3D-printed prototype has lower losses than the commercial section. This difference fits with simulations of ideal WR-28 sections, considering copper with a roughness of $0.4 \mu\text{m}$ for the 3D-printed piece and aluminum with $1 \mu\text{m}$ of

1–5 are similar, with some discrepancies in terms of losses or small frequency shifts. There is a difference of 0.25 dB in loss between prototypes 1–5. This difference is mainly due to the metallization process of each piece, as the resulting roughness has a high impact on losses.

After discarding prototype 6 due to insufficient metallization, Figure 11(c) shows that the best results are obtained with prototypes 1, 2, and 3, and the worst result with prototype 5. This implies that the roughness and conductivity of the metallization in the first case is the best, while 5 presents a higher roughness. A larger variation occurs in the four-way divider in Figure 12(c). This can be caused by the effect of the load terminations used in the measurement, which do not match perfectly. Table 2 shows the results of the average losses measured in the band of interest (28–30 GHz), the weight of the pieces, and whether we had to correct bended pieces. Considering that the straight section has a length of 90 mm, the average losses obtained

Figure 12. Simulations (SIM) and measurements (IDs 1–6) of the four-way power divider for the six prototypes: (a) the reflection, (b) the transmission, and (c) a detailed view of the transmission. Only one output of each is displayed for easy viewing.

roughness for the commercial section, as shown in Figure 14(a). For the case of the WR-10 sections in Figure 14(b), there is agreement between the measurement of the commercial section and the ideal simulation with gold and a roughness of $0.075 \mu\text{m}$. The measurement of the 3D-printed WR-10 section fits well with a slightly modified WR-10 section that differs from $2.54 \times 1.27 \text{ mm}$ to $2.42 \times 1.22 \text{ mm}$ and rounded corners with a radius of 0.15 mm . These values were obtained considering the mean values of the measurements of the two flanges of the 3D-printed WR-10 section using a microscope. Figure 15 presents the microphotograph of this straight section along with the measured values. The simulated curves of the ideal and modified WR-10 sections are shown in Figure 14(b) with a roughness of $0.55 \mu\text{m}$. Of particular interest is the weight reduction of plastic parts, which is an advantage for satellite-embedded equipment or other applications that require lightness.

TABLE 2. A comparison of results and average losses for the GGW prototypes.

ID	Material	Bending	Loss Section (dB)	Loss Divider (dB)	Weight (g)
1	Nanotool	No	0.23	0.54	115
2	Accura	Yes	0.18	0.32	95
3	Accura	Yes	0.29	0.50	95
4	Accura	No	0.33	0.37	65
5	Material D	No	0.40	0.47	90
6	VisiJet	No	7.30	8.41	55

Figure 13. A 100-mm-long WR-28 section printed in 3D next to a 100-mm commercial section: (a) the side view and (c) the front view. A 31-mm-long section of WR-10 printed in 3D next to a 35.1-mm-long commercial section: (b) the side view and (d) the front view.

Conclusions

This article compared various metal-coated 3D-printed waveguide devices using GGW technology, WR-10 and WR-28. The results obtained are positive in most

Figure 14. A measurement comparison of the response of the (a) WR-28 and (b) WR-10 pieces with simulations fitted to the material and roughness. The curve Cu $0.55 \mu\text{m}$ modified corresponds to the WR-10 structure with modifications of width, height, and rounding of corners in accordance with the measured (Meas.) dimensions in Figure 15. Al: aluminum; Au: gold; Cu: copper.

TABLE 3. A comparison of the results and average losses for the WR-28 and WR-10 prototypes.

Device	Average Losses (dB/m)	Weight (g)
Commercial WR-28	2.33	110
3D-printed WR-28	1.17	70
Commercial WR-10	3.48	15
3D-printed WR-10	10.48	3

Figure 15. Microphotographs of the input of the 3D-printed WR-10 section with the measured values for height, width, and rounded corners.

cases, with low losses and a great similarity between measurements and simulation. We emphasize the importance of the metal-coating process of the plastic structures because an insufficient thickness of metallization prevents the correct guidance of the electromagnetic fields. In addition, the roughness of this metal layer has a strong influence on total losses, so it is desirable to attain glossy surfaces. Finally, the comparison between commercial and 3D-printed WR-28 and WR-10 waveguides makes clear the great potential of additive manufacturing in producing mm-wave components having low cost, weight, and loss, as well as great design versatility.

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